

[研究文章 Research Article]

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Notes on Two Species of *Acleris* Hübner, [1825] (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae, Tortricinae, Tortricini) from Taiwan

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Abstract. The present study provides images of the adults and genitalia of *Acleris japonica* (Walsingham, 1900) and *A. lacordairana* (Duponchel, 1836), along with their distribution records in Taiwan. The host plant utilization and seasonal adult forms of *A. japonica* in Taiwan are also confirmed.

Key words: distribution records, host plant association, *Acleris*

Introduction

Acleris Hübner, [1825] is the largest genus in the tribe Tortricini, comprising more than 200 species (Gilligan et al., 2018). Kawabe et al. (1992) listed 29 species of *Acleris* from Taiwan but they did not provide details on the examined vouchers. Among them, *Acleris japonica* (Walsingham, 1900) and *A. lacordairana* (Duponchel, 1836) are the two species in Taiwan characterized by their forewing with white ground color and some grey or brown blotches on the distal half. Both species were first recorded in the country by Kawabe et al. (1992), but no further studies have examined specimens from Taiwan since then. The present study aims to provide images of the genitalia and adults based on Taiwanese specimens of both species and report some morphological differences between populations from Taiwan and other regions.

Materials and methods

Voucher specimens were collected by light traps or reared from the host plant. Abdomens were removed for dissection following the methods provided by Lu et al. (2024) and the genitalia were mounted in Euparal for further examination and preservation. Images of adults were taken with a Nikon Z8 digital camera NIKKOR Z MC 105mm f/2.8 VR S lens for figs. 1a, b, and e, and a Canon EOS RP with a Canon EF 100mm f/2.8 Macro USM or Canon RF100mm f/2.8L MACRO IS USM lens for figs. 1c, d, and f. Genitalia images were taken with a Nikon D7200 camera attached to a Leica DM500 microscope. Terminology of wing patterns and genitalia follows Razowski (1987, 2003). The scientific names of the host plants follow POWO (2025). The type information refers to Gilligan et al., 2018. Examined vouchers are deposited in NTM or will be deposited in NMNS.

Abbreviations

NTM: National Taiwan Museum, Taipei

NMNS: National Museum of Natural Science, Taichung

BMNH: National History Museum, London, United Kingdom

Results

Acleris japonica (Walsingham, 1900)

日本長翅捲蛾（首次建議中文名）

(Figs. 1a–d, 2a, c–d)

Oxygrapha japonica Walsingham, 1900: 373. (Type information: Holotype: sex unknown, Japan, "Hon-shu, Nagano, Oiwake". (BMNH))

Acleris japonica; Yasuda, 1965: 29, figs 34, 78, 127, 128; Razowski, 1966: 431, figs 628–631, pl. XXXII, figs 6–7; Yasuda, 1975: 183, figs 176, 177, 521, 522, 651; Kawabe et. al., 1992: 103; Jinbo, 2013: 166, pl. 4–13, figs 11–13.

Specimens examined. TAIWAN. 2♂♂, Taitung Co., Beinan Township, Zhiben, 13. III. 2023, reared from *Zelkova serrata*, emgd. 4/16. IV. 2023, HSUM23C65, Y. M. Hsu Coll. (Gen. Prep. YYLU-819) (NMNS); 1♀, Taichung City, Heping, Wushikeng Research Center, 850m, 27. IV. 2024, Y. Y. Lu, Y. M. Hsu & J. Y. Liang Coll. (Gen. Prep. YYL0050) (NMNS). 1♀, Taichung City, Heping, Anma Villa, 2250 m, 11. XII. 2022, S. Wu Coll. (NTM); 2♂♂, Hsinchu County, Jianshi, Mamei, 1000 m, 4. I. 2025, leg. S. Wu Coll. (NTM).

Diagnosis

This species can be recognized by its white ground color, several scattered light grey strigulae, and a large brown blotch on the distal half. Both male and female genitalia of this species resemble those of *Acleris kochiella* (Goeze, 1783), which is distributed from Europe to China. In the male genitalia of *A. japonica*, the socii are broader, the plate-shaped ventral process at the postmedial sacculus is present, and there are two cornuti, whereas in *A. kochiella* the socii is narrower, the plate-shaped ventral process is absent, and there are five cornuti. In the female genitalia, the antrum of *A. japonica* is well sclerotized, whereas that of *A. kochiella* is weakly sclerotized.

Host plants

Zelkova serrata (Ulmaceae) (Yasuda, 1965), also confirmed from Taiwan in the present study, *Quercus acutissima* (Fagaceae) (Razowski, 1966), and *Viola grypoceras* (Violaceae) (Jinbo, 2013).

Distribution

Japan, Korea, and Taiwan (Jinbo, 2013).

Remarks

In Japan, this species has been reported with two seasonal forms, the winter form and the summer form (Jinbo, 2013). In Taiwan, we also observed two seasonal forms. In the winter form (Fig. 1a, 1b), the basal region of the forewing has more scattered grey strigulae and the distal brown blotch is clearly divided into a subapical blotch and a tornal blotch. In the summer form (figs. 1c, 1d), the basal region of the forewing has fewer scattered grey strigulae and the boundary between the subapical blotch and the tornal blotch is blurred. There is only one minor difference between the Japanese population and the Taiwanese population in the female genitalia, where the size of the corpus bursae in Japanese populations is distinctly smaller than in Taiwan.

Acleris lacordairana (Duponchel, 1836)

灰斑長翅捲蛾 (首次建議中文名)

(Figs. 1e, 1f, 2b, 2e–f)

Peronea lacordairana "Duponchel, in Godart", 1836: 562, pl. 266, fig 1. (Type information: Syntype(s): sex unknown, France. [Unknown])

Teras lacordairiana Guenée, 1845: 144. [misspelling]

Acleris roxana Razowski & Yasuda, 1964: 87, figs 20–22, 35.

Acleris lacordairana; Yasuda, 1965: 29, figs 33, 76, 124, 125; Razowski, 1966: 415, figs 589–602, pl. XXXI, fig 3; Yasuda, 1975: 182, figs 173–175, 519, 520; Kawabe et. al., 1992: 103; Byun & Yan, 2004: 95, figs 2, 5; Jinbo, 2013: 168, pl. 4–13, figs 33–35.

Specimens examined. TAIWAN. 2♀♀, Kaohsiung City, Taoyuan Dist., Tianchih, 2280m, 22. VI. 2022, Y. Y. Lu, C. W. Huang & Z. L. Chen Coll. (Gen. Prep. YYLU-628) (NMNS); 1♂, Hualien Co., Xiulin Township, Bilu Divine Tree, 2150m, 12. VII. 2022, Y. Y. Lu, C. W. Huang & Z. L. Chen Coll. (Gen. Prep. YYLU-662) (NMNS); 1♂, Nantou Co. Renai Township, Songquangang, 2541m, 7. VIII. 2023, Y. Y. Lu, Y. M. Hsu & F. R. Kung Coll. (NMNS). 1♂, Taichung City, Heping, Anma Villa, 2250 m, 11. XII. 2022, S. Wu Coll. (NTM); 1♂, Hsinchu County, Guanwu, 2000 m, 29. III. 2011, S. Wu & W. C. Chang Coll. (NTM).

Diagnosis

This species is similar to *Acleris takeuchii* Razowski & Yasuda, 1964. *A. lacordairana* can be distinguished by the following characters: basal forewing with more scattered dark scales; dark brown strigulae on the basal forewing absent; saccus with a distinct concavity ventrally as opposed to a strong ventral thorn basally in *A. takeuchii*; posterior margin of the sterigma more strongly concave.

Host plants

Acer rufinerve Siebold & Zucc. (Sapindaceae) (Jinbo, 2013), and *Ulmus* sp. (Ulmaceae) (Razowski, 1966).

Distribution

Europe, Russia, China, Korea, Japan, and Taiwan (Jinbo, 2013).

Remarks

There are minor differences in the number and shape of cornuti between the population from Taiwan, which has three, and those from other regions, which have two that are more slender.

Figures 1. The habitus of *Acleris* species in Taiwan. 1a-b. *A. japonica* (Walsingham, 1900), winter form; 1c-d. Ditto, summer form; e-f. *A. lacordairana* (Duponchel, 1836). Photos by Shipher Wu (1a, b, e); Yi-Yang Lu (1c, d, f).

Figures 2. The genitalia of *Acleris* species in Taiwan. 1a. *A. japonica* (Walsingham, 1900), male; 1b. *A. lacordairana* (Duponchel, 1836), female; c. *A. japonica*, female; d. Ditto, magnified image of signum; e. *A. lacordairana*, female; f. magnified image of signum. Photos by Yi-Yang Lu.

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臺灣產兩種長翅捲蛾屬物種之註記（鱗翅目：捲蛾科：捲蛾亞科：捲蛾族）

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摘要：本研究旨在提供日本長翅捲蛾 (*Acleris japonica* (Walsingham, 1900)) 及灰斑長翅捲蛾 (*A. lacordairana* (Duponchel, 1836)) 兩個物種的成蟲標本照與交尾器照，並記錄其在臺灣的分布情形。前者在臺灣的寄主植物利用與成蟲季節型亦獲確認。

關鍵字：分布紀錄、寄主植物關聯、長翅捲蛾屬